

The pandemic is a global problem of the 21st century and His consequences

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Abstract : This in the article pandemic during social to the defense needs population layer support is needed population layer from poverty release , social to the defense needs families every bilaterally support regarding Neighborhood and the family support Ministry by done increased affairs analysis given

Key words : pandemic , social protection , world economy his important factor

Access Many countries for COVID-19 is terrible wake up it has been . Continue doing crisis society problems reflection is fatal effects the government system for example not seen roads with test is conducting . In this period in Uzbekistan the first in line decline conditions economy and coronavirus with to fight for health storage system stability attention was directed . The COVID-19 pandemic during himself insulation to do mode people a lot the time family members surrounded by to transfer forced did The congregation in the field this family to relationships how influence to do about discussions there is . Neighborhood and the family support Ministry " Neighborhood and family " scientific research at the institute on May 10, 2021 held " Pandemic conditions in the family peace and harmony save current duties and on the subject of " problems ". republic scientific and practical convention our country scientific in his life to himself special to prestige have was to the convention turned . Conference activity pandemic topic with related way family and family of the institute to our country special all economic , social , spiritual , psychological problems discussion to do focused Conference in the work Neighborhood and the family support Ministry representative (GMMarufova) of the republic different about 80 of the regions participants , including Karakalpakstan Republic of Tashkent , Surkhandarya ,

Fergana , Jizzakh , Samarkand, Namangan, Khorezm , Bukhara , Navoi regions representatives participation they did

If organizations in the section looking after in our case , Moscow is a state university , preparation and their qualification increase territorial centers , Tashkent medicine Academy , Tashkent state economy University , Fergana state University , UzR FA MAM, Uzbekistan Republic President in the presence of Strategic and interregional studies Institute , Forecasting and macroeconomic studies Institute , Uzbekistan National University , Jizzakh state pedagogy Institute , Uzbekistan Republic President in the presence of State management Academy , Uzbekistan state the world languages University , Samarkand State University , Nizami TDPU in the name of Namangan State University , RBIMMSMF, Khorezm province people education Department , International islam academy , Zo'rlik from using injury saw individuals rehabilitation to do and adaptation and own to his soul intention of doing prevention get Republican center , Consultative-psychological centers such as dozen organizations attended to the problems scientific research achievement , conclusion and recommendations work exit to himself special openness and transparency , scientific freedom and scientists rights guarantees provision , subject circles non-limitation "Neighborhood and family ” scientific research of the institute to himself special to tradition is spinning . "Neighborhood and family ” scientific research institute while in our country authoritative and neighborhood and family issues according to scientific the team unifying to the center , neighborhood and to the family circle views scientific from the cricket the conductor to the platform , prospective development factors scientific confirmed giver experiment , analysis and forecast to the base turning around is going

This of the subject purpose and tasks :

" Pandemic conditions in the family peace and harmony save current duties and to the issue of " problems ". dedicated . The subject is very current of the subject relevance not only pandemic or quarantine condition with is determined , perhaps his

relevance PEACE AND HARMONY IN THE FAMILY - all peoples , culture and civilizations the main family in history value that of the family column and main condition the fact that it is our people national tradition the fact that with is determined . That is in the family peace and harmony protected , respected , the head of the family to live condition , his power and charter is also This is a law , this is a demand from the coronavirus from the coronovirus , which has been there before and so on to be will remain . Therefore , peace and harmony storage is eternal value , historical heritage , national tradition and a person spirituality is an indicator .

The Qur'an It is said in verse 21 of Sura Rum of Karim according to " You comfort you will find for from yourselves couples we created and between you ingenuity and kindness appear we did Of course , in this thinking who does people for signs it is said . Baqara and in verse 208 of the sura , " O faith brought ! Close up peace to work come in !" it is noted that

Uzbek people in his thinking from long ago peace in honor bride Uzbek people in proverbs to be told "The world is peaceful - my room calm " , " Peace - the most good Ointment " , " Calm let's go garden flowers " , " Peace - happiness , health - throne " , " Peace with people blue , rain with - earth " , " Peace - prosperity "companion" . Accordingly , be tolerant , patient , satisfied , courageous our people in Ardoga was this huge inheritance , i.e in the family peace and harmony Today is also the honor what we do necessity period is a requirement . Therefore , a person which in the circumstances , which in the situation , how without from the beginning definitely nazar , in the family ingenuity and kindness establish a family peace and harmony space convert , family members in the middle harmony relationships installation , family to hearts ointment that manifestation to do on the way service what we do it is necessary So it is holy in our book said this current task both men and women towards said holy the word and we are our youth that's exactly it out of the way to go our invitation and incentive what we do it is necessary The family is in it love , kindness ,

peace , tranquility , harmony , kindness mercy installation for is made . So , thinking did a person peace and peace of mind bonds strengthening from the way goes

Family is secular is a concept . Family to a person this in the world tasks in execution holy space as appointment done Family is a person given is a gift . From the family the goal and it is offspring . Offspring not only physically , maybe consciousness , thinking , knowledge , skill , craft the point in terms of it's also like that to do necessary Therefore , the offspring that's it making - society that's it to do equal to will come . The world scale International health storage organization on March 11, 2020 regarding "COVID-19". the pandemic announcement did We have since March 14 country across quarantine announcement done . We have all been here for about 1.5 years since that's it until time in general imagination do it didn't get in the circumstances we live We are all " Coronavirus , Covid generations" . Mask wear does not melt doing it , all of us our wallet next to one mask of course adding to put aspiring period our descendants . With that together , we are all - everyone difficulties I'm walking overcame increasing , different situations fast and factoriality with solution going , the whole nation pain in front waist tight tie , own in our responsibility tasks Sincerely done coming generation our representatives . We are the people as from labor , work , creativity we didn't stop . Today's being conducted conference of this bright is an example . Losses it has been . Losses a person patient , resistant , calm and clever to be provided . Corona virus of the pandemic to Uzbekistan special from the main features one this - we united , difficulties overcame passed , work system We did not slow down , economic to the crisis come in We didn't leave , the people heavy light we tried to do , prayers hand we opened , our prayers answer it has been . As a result - in our country losses the number is minimal it has been . Corona virus period whole one generation , from small pulling all of us own in oil fried took us people as , nation as cooked and more on the stone returns . Uzbek people from time immemorial peace welcome saw him appreciating came wise is the people . Accordingly , in Uzbekistan coronavirus pandemic in time in families socio-spiritual environment about speaking if we are , himself bright

manifestation reached feature is one from the side some of families economic situation deterioration , maintenance issues difficulties the presence of relatives in migration that is , our weddings that it stopped despite our families strengthened , kind be we started , loss content deeper understand we started , health and health according to scientific affairs take went NEW YORK/GENEVA/WASHINGTON, D.C., April 3, 2020: Today the world health storage organization (WHO) and UN Children fund (UNICEF) ¹against COVID-19 solidarity fund through cooperation to do about agreement that they signed announcement they did This is it cooperation United Nations Organization and Emblem of the Swiss Philanthropy Foundation of Switzerland in support of basis put and historical to the point have defeating COVID -19 for solidarity fund within against COVID - 19 solidarity fund of JSS strategic preparation and answer measures plan based on done to be increased for example to unprecedented global measures help to give in order to Created . This agreement within 127 million dollars of the fund more than has been common from the funds the first part of UNICEF whole in the world to the defense the most needs children and local teams with to work directed activities will be directed to funding .«Covid-19 is for example not seen pandemic to him against urgent measures to see for urgent global solidarity is required , " said WHO director - general , Dr. Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus . — I am UNICEF's solidarity to the fund added I am very pleased . of UNICEF funds attraction reach and programs done increase regarding big experience people his life save to stay in order to closely cooperation to do service will do ."

This a total of funds for the prevention of COVID-19 get , determine and treatment according to local communities and medicine employees knowledge and skills increase and necessary equipment with provide for is spent . These countries for health storage opportunities expand and of COVID-19 , in particular women , children and weak social to groups relatively social effect to reduce possibility will give . From this except , efforts prevention vaccines and efficient treatment methods work exit

¹ . [https:// www . unicef org](https://www.unicef.org)

regarding studies accelerates. This cooperation within main partner as , UNICEF the most to the defense needs in countries families and teams belongs to events with cover to get to coordination leadership does Water , sanitation and hygiene tools have to be , of infections prevention get events these are including Also his local teams with work plans and country programs within , scientific based on recommendations through UNICEF children , parents , guardians , social service employees , teachers and medicine in the field experts supports . "This is too much. " important extraordinary requiring action very important extraordinary situation being , we whole the world community , in particular physical individuals , corporations , foundations , governments and another organizations to solidarity we will call - he emphasized of UNICEF performer director Henrietta Faure. — UNICEF solidarity to the jaw from joining very I am satisfied . This is health storage and sanitation system improvement according to our actions to activate , of COVID-19 with a chain reaction as a result health storage system too much except pressure under the rest one at the time the most needs families protection to do help will give ."

SARS-CoV2 virus overcome the COVID-19 pandemic completion is the whole the world health storage system one from more period during face came the most an important global challenge is considered Those who have recovered struggling next mutations or complications - today medicine are problems . At one time in itself doctors every trip another to patients help display and them in treatment necessary was methods to use they are trying The virus better to understand and to patients help display for wide in the circle thinking and to professional knowledge have to be it is necessary Short time inside next Adamed International At the conference the world according to one how many a thousand expert participation is enough " Pandemic with again one year and health storage to the system new calls named event on April 22-23, 2021 online way will be held. Eng last scientific to research based on knowledge , experts with cooperation and innovations today's until the day to the coronavirus against the only effective in fighting experience to be remains Modern of medicine important to

the calls in response Adamed second times Europe and of Asia nine from the country doctors International to the conference offer is doing This is it event against COVID-19 struggle according to last news of the pandemic diary clinical practice how change observation and doctors opposite standing to problems dedicated . Lectures online way Polish , English , Russian and Spanish to their languages translation done without to the air is transmitted .

. Adamed II International the main moderator of the conference is prof. Andrzej M. Fal in Warsaw Internal affairs and administration of the ministry central clinical hospital , allergy , lungs diseases and internal diseases clinical department chief and Poland public health society management council is the president . His I think it is such as project doctors high way support means : First over 10,000 at the convention doctor participation did Event in the beginning two day during our patients in treatment and COVID- 19 for us to stop useful to be possible was every one the problem practical way discussion we did A few months later , the pandemic serious color took , but we vaccination we started and to the coronavirus against to fight about some to knowledge have we were Come on , more than that to knowledge have to be for Adamed II International At the conference let 's meet tdi. International tourism until 2020 fast because it grew rapidly all countries tourism sector fast and significant income source realized that without , international tourists more involvement and from tourism coming income to increase field resources work exit and to manage the field more importance to give there is is making an effort was 2019 year in december started a pandemic in the field serious to changes take came. of the pandemic huge and deep effect economic, social and medical problems come due to exit it has been . Globally , as well as governments by his spreading prevention to get strictly measures seen (border closure , travel restrictions , national blockages, restaurant and of hotels closure). of COVID19 the climax take as a result , many tourist destinations in 2020 insulation measures and travel bans , orders void to do and local logistics to stop forced they were Also like this evolutionary steps tourism during the pandemic heavy to the situation

incomes , signs save to stay for there is has been alternatives in terms of the most affected network to stay reason it has been . of the field to other supporting (dependent) networks negative multiplier impact , economic significance and global the work seats loss exactly tourism recovery related to mitigating the impact of COVID-19 in sectors for strong help and demanded support .²

of the pandemic negative effect Uzbekistan together did not pass In particular , he came to Uzbekistan in 2020 foreign tourists number for 2019 relatively four from the bar to more decreased About Uzbekistan Tourism development state Aziz Abduhakimov, chairman of the committee known did His according to his words , it has passed year during 1.5 million tourists to Uzbekistan visit ordered He came to Uzbekistan in 2019 foreign tourists number for 2018 increased by 26.2 percent , 6.7 [16] million people organize reached A. Abduhakimov foreign tourists decrease in flow as a result come came out economic crisis mitigation in order to main attention local tourism to develop being directed stressed. Quarantine during Uzbekistan Republic Tourism development state committee tourism on is working Including in the field of tourism entrepreneurship subjects support in order to pandemic during to them a number benefits , tax holidays and subsidies to give order current done An example for , tourism and service enterprises until January 1, 2021 (this year February in the month the president by year until the end extended) land tax from paying free social tax preferential paying at the rate (1%) , profitability the rate is 50 percent drop off and so on . From this except for entrepreneurs interest-free loans , grants and subsidies present done. Uzbekistan President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, June 2020 in the month quarantine limitations Strictly did without internal and external tourism support measures the decision on signed was In the Republic For Uzbekistan safe tourism according to special program started working . "Uzbekistan: Safe travel GUARANTEED" (Uzbekistan . Safe travel guaranteed ») today until the day activity to international

² Whitmore DJ Vnutrennyaya sila leadera. Coaching bro method administration persona - lom Searching for Performance : Growing Human Potential and Purpose. - M.: " Alpina Pabli - lion ", 2012. - 312 p. 1

standards according to sanitation standards compliance provides. This of the program main purpose is foreign tourists attraction in reaching Uzbekistan throughout the territory safe travel to do possible from promotion consists of. Final conclusions announcement of being done delay while experts between approximate disagreements reason that it is not note until May 9 , 2022 more than 192 viruses country and in the area of 517 million inhabitants in love man infected ; More than 6,250,000 man disease because of death from 472 million in love man while recovered. China , Europe , Iran , South Korea and in the USA pandemic furnaces surface came. Virus to the flu similar way when coughing and axis when giving released drops through person to person infect. Virus in the patient disease symptoms surface when it comes the most contagious although it is a disease signs appear from being to others before infection can illness symptoms usually five in the day appear but it is period from 2 to 14 days continue reach can Of the disease main symptoms fever , cough and breath is a squeeze . illness in the patient pneumonia and sharp breath receiving distress syndrome cause release can The same against COVID -19 vaccine or drug no . Disease manage symptoms treatment and help from therapy consists of illness spreading prevention get for hands washing , when coughing mouth blocking from others (especially oneself away from those who don't feel well in the distance to be recommendation will be done . The virus infected guess doing 14 days to individuals during themselves insulation to do recommendation illness spreading prevention get in order to travel to do restriction , quarantine , curfew hours , events later to leave and void to do and institutions to close such as measures was seen . In particular , the virus spread started Hubei province to quarantine received , Italy , Spain , France , Czech Republic and in Germany country across quarantine current , [China and South in Korea Commandant hour current done , different countries boundaries close closed or to tourists against restrictions current , airport and train at the stations control measures to the road put ,[19] the virus is widespread spreading in the regions travel to do against recommendations announcement done .In at least 115 countries university and schools close or some in

the regions closed , this measures from 950 million in love student to the activity influence showed .in Uzbekistan the virus infect situation for the first time on March 15 note done

The pandemic is global series socio-economic difficulties cause released , sports and cultural events later be left or void to be done cause became , [medicine , electronics goods and food products deficiency surface coming about to concerns reason became .[26][27] Also on the Internet virus and pandemic about wrong data and conspiracy theories hit ,[28][29] different countries xenophobia and racism cases observed , to panic fell buyers toilet paper such as goods a lot amount buy take observed .[30] July 2021 In the WHO chairman Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus vaccinations due to of the coronavirus to vaccines resistant strain appear to be possible said [31]. Illness spreading prevention get in order to travel to do restriction , quarantine , curfew hours , events later to leave and void to do and institutions to close such as measures was seen . In particular , the virus spread started Hubei province to quarantine received , Italy , Spain , France , Czech Republic and in Germany country across quarantine current done, China and South in Korea Commandant hour current was done , different countries boundaries close closed or to tourists against restrictions current done, airport and train at the stations control measures to the road put , the virus is wide spreading in the regions travel to do against recommendations announcement done in at least 115 countries university and schools close or some in the regions closed , this measures from 950 million in love student to the activity influence showed. In Uzbekistan the virus infect situation for the first time on March 15 note done³

The pandemic is global series socio-economic difficulties cause released, sports and cultural events later be left or void to be done cause medicine , electronics goods and food products deficiency surface coming about to concerns reason Also , there is a virus on the Internet and pandemic about wrong data and conspiracy theories hit , various countries xenophobia and racism cases observed , to panic fell buyers toilet

³. Shekshnya S. Kak effectively upravlyat svobodnymi lyudmi: Coaching. M.: Alpina Publisher , 2011. - S. 208

paper such as goods a lot amount buy take observed . July 2021 In the WHO chairman Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus vaccinations due to of the coronavirus to vaccines resistant strain appear to be possible said. Duration : 4 minutes and 13 seconds.4:13 Subtitles available. CC Coronavirus disease Video about (script) World health storage organization Address of the head of April 2021 in the month the world health storage organization head Tedros Adhanom the world leaders immediately with vaccination didn't start 10 million doses to countries coronavirus the vaccine to separate called ,, to the coronavirus against to the vaccine have was to countries this to the drug the need there is countries 10 million doses for vaccine separation asking appeal i did But the state from the leaders still answer " I'm waiting ," he said noted Tedros Adhanom. The COVID-19 pandemic us many p to act side by side forced is doing The virus directly destructive effect eliminate reach for countries for example not seen fast measures , that's it including boundaries to close entered However , the virus is the limit does n't know He is all to countries effect showed We have there is was humanity feeling us in combining continue reach need A lot of people to his life ground to be and to our society effect to the global pandemic against struggle whole in the world international cooperation and solidarity expand and requires strengthening . Pandemic cover get and to him against to fight for cooperation , transparency and scientific to knowledge based on coordinated international action is necessary . We all countries , especially developing and less developed countries as well health storage systems less developed and to conflicts subject to has been countries for serious from the threat we are worried . From this besides , we are refugees and another to the place moved people face coming sure from danger worry we are getting We know that the pandemic every one of a person physical and mental to health the most high level serious risk gives birth .

Summary:

Pandemic cover get and to him against to fight for cooperation , transparency and scientific to knowledge based on coordinated international action is necessary . We all countries , especially developing and less developed countries as well health storage systems less developed and to conflicts subject to has been countries for serious from the threat we are worried . From this besides , we are refugees and another to the place moved people face coming sure from danger worry We are taking we know it's a pandemic every one of a person physical and mental to health the most high level serious risk gives birth With that together , extraordinary in the situation democracy and the law priority principles compliance to do very important We all governments this to the threat against to fight for being seen measures proportionate and necessary , legal to goals reach , legal non-discrimination , and international to the laws , that's it including a person rights compliance to be done to provide we call Gender approach principles compliance to do very important Non-discrimination to politics As for us , we are the UN Man rights according to High Commissioner's statement on March 6 we support , then to the crisis against measures in application dignity and a person rights attention in the center standing need and this measures global and a person rights based on to be need mentioned.related to COVID-19 crisis health preservation , well-being and collective our safety for a lot bilaterally of institutions importance proved We health storage in the field international relationships coordinator the world health storage Organization (WHO), as well as United Nations Organization , Jahan bank and another international and regional of organizations of the crisis social and economic consequences coordination and consistent done increase regarding efforts complete We support United Nations Organization Secretary General Antonio Guterres immediately with whole in the world grass to open to stop calling we support . Armed to conflicts check put , military actions immediately with to stop and whole our strength and our reserves our planet in front standing main danger — to the coronavirus against to fight to spend time came Medical and humanitarian to employees their lives save stay important role sincerely for gratitude let us know and own our lives save to stay

according to own duties perform for necessary has been conditions save to stay and support own upon us we can Citizenship society from the representatives Thank you , they persistence with the most defenseless people own for protection is taking We to the epidemic of COVID-19 against in the struggle being seen measures we approve . We are in the UN's COVID-19 pandemic humanity help in the global plan participation reach through contribution to add we are ready We are the Secretary General of the UN less and average profitable to the states against COVID -19 to fight and rehabilitation fund of the crisis social and economic effect overcame transition to recovery help to give and to this in response coordination and cooperation strengthen according to efforts we support . Health storage in the field duties : Today in the day from the pandemic come coming out the most current medical , economic and political to tasks separately attention focus it is necessary We are united Nations of the organization's COVID-19 effect according to common responsibility and international solidarity to strengthen has been call , in particular , WHO to the epidemic against health storage events in coordination WHO role we support . We are in a pandemic against struggle for , that's it including whole the world across health storage system strengthening for enough allocation of funds on we are working . Medicines and vaccines there is when to provide them universally directed events we support .

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